

ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE AND DEPRESSION IN POST BURN PATIENTS IN BURN AND PLASTIC SURGERY CENTER HAYATABAD

Naeem Ullah Shinwari^{*1}, Aleena Mustafa², Faiza Jamil³, Ishfaq Ahmed⁴, Rahat Aman⁵, Sabar Mina⁶

^{*1}Physiotherapist At Shifa Rehab and Research Center Peshawar, Lecturer Tariq Jee Institute of Allied Health Science, Peshawar Shifa Rehab and Research Center Peshawar, Jee Institute of Allied Health Science, Peshawar

²Lecturer, DPT Department of Allied Health Science City University of Sign and Information Technology, CEO Back and Motion Physio Work City University of Sign and Information Technology, Back and Motion Physio Work

³physiotherapist At Afridi Medical Complex Peshawar Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Department Afridi Medical Complex Peshawar

⁴Physiotherapist At Akbar Medical Canter Peshawar Akbar Medical Canter Peshawar

⁵Physiotherapist Physio Rehab Trainer at Body Strong Gym Peshawar Body Strong Gym Peshawar

⁶Associate Physiotherapist, Rehman Medical Institute Peshawar Rehman Medical Institute Peshawar

^{*1}naemphysio58@gmail.com, ²Aleenamustafa897@gmail.com, ³faizajamil761@gmail.com,
⁴4uishfaq@gmail.com, ⁵haseenakhan3737@gmai.com, ⁶sabar.mina@rmi.edu.pk

^{*1}<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4604-4740>

Corresponding Author: *

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ABSTRACT

Background: Burns are injuries that can affect anyone, anywhere, at any time. Burn is a severe public health issue that have a significant impact on both society and the healthcare the aim of our study is to assess the quality of life and depression in post burn patients.

Objectives: The objectives of the study were to Evaluate Quality of Life and depression in Post-Burn Patients

Methodology: A cross-sectional descriptive study was carried out in Tertiary care hospitals of Peshawar. A total of 282 burn injuries participants were enrolled in this study. The sample size was calculated through raosoft online software with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%. Data were collected from those burn patients who gave written or verbal permission and met our inclusion criteria through non-probability convenient sampling method using assessment tools PHQ-9 for depression and EQ5D3L for quality of life

Result: The study included 282 participants, out of which 168 were males (59.6%) and 114 were females (40.4%). The participants had an average age of 33 years, ranging from 18 to 50 years. The majority of the participants (41.5%) fall within the range of 31 to 45 years. Male were the predominant gender (59.6%) of the sample. The most frequent causes of burn were Flame burns, accounted 57.1% followed by electrical burn (15.2%),

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Scald burn (12.1%), chemical burn 28 (9.9%) and Thermal burn 16 (5.7%). Quality of life were impaired more in males. Most of the participants with burns injuries experience major problems in usual activities followed by problem in self-care. Depression was statistically found very common in burn patients. Males were predominant in depression. A significant difference was observed among the groups according to PHQ-9 grading of depression. 17.0% cases were in minimal depression, 18.8% in mild, 20.2% in moderate, 15.6% in moderately severe and 28.4% were severe depressed.

Conclusion: It is concluded that the findings of the present study indicate that burn injuries have a negative impact on several dimensions of EQ-5D (QoL). Various risk factors including age, gender, occupational status, anatomical location, etiology, depth and percentage of Total Body Surface Area (%TBSA) burned, affect the outcomes of QoL in burn patients. Additionally, the presence of depression related to post-burn trauma had a significant negative impact on the quality of life. Trauma in any form has a profound impact on the mind of the victim lead to depression and brings about changes in the whole personality of the patient.

Keywords: Post burn, Quality of life, patient health questionnaire-9, Outpatient department

INTRODUCTION

Burns are major health problem and fourth frequent cause of trauma, following falls, road incidences worldwide. Burn Injuries can be caused by friction, cold, heat, electricity, chemicals, or electricity, but most burns are caused by hot liquids, explosives, or fire (1). Burn injury effects can create many difficulties for patients. The most common problems are hypertrophic scars, joint stiffness, poor motor function (such as muscle weakness, lack of coordination and decreased mobility), mental disorders, and difficulty with daily life activities, and psychological. (2). Burns are terrible injuries that frequently cause a great deal of morbidity, emotional distress, and a reduced quality of life. (4).

The American Burn Association (ABA) in 2019 reports that, overall, flame burns are still the majority of injuries in the USA (41%), with scalds second at (31%). Chemical (3.5%) and electrical burn injuries (3.6%) occur much less commonly (5). The World Health Organization defines a healthy lifestyle as a person's perception of his place and life within the culture and values in which he lives. Goals, expectations, and norms and values relevant to that context (6). Burns that are left untreated or treatment is delayed. Depression is one of the most common psychological symptoms of patients suffering from burns(12). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), burns occur in approximately 90% of the world in underdeveloped countries, and approximately 40% of burn deaths occur in Southeast Asia (13).

According to reports, the majority of burn patients have a reduced quality of life. The term "health-related quality of life" (HRQOL) is broad and has a multifaceted definition that includes self-reported measures of both mental and physical health. (15). Measuring the quality of life (QoL) of burn survivors is essential for any burn service provider in order to analyze outcomes and enhance care. As the number of burn victims who are destined to live with diminished physical and mental ability rises (16). The quality of life (QoL) of burn injury victims is greatly influenced by a number of factors, including how they respond to their injuries, when they begin treatment, the support of their families, the effectiveness of their care, their diet, their occupational and physical therapists, and their counseling. Many domains are impacted by QoL (17). Physical and psychological functioning, as well as day-to-day activities, can all be significantly harmed by burns. In short, HRQL domains are frequently compromised. The patient's age and gender, the amount of total body surface area (%TBSA) burned, the length of hospital stay, the body area that was damaged, the amount of time since the injury, and the psychological effects of the burns are all potential significant factors (18). One of the most prevalent psychological side effects following a burn injury is depression. Patients often experience hopelessness if they stay in the hospital for several weeks, and this hopelessness can eventually result in chronic depression (19). According to one of the few studies that looked at depression two years after an injury, up to 42% of burn survivors experience moderate-to-severe depressive symptoms two years after their injury. The prevalence of depression actually increased between the first and second

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year (20). The two most often studied conditions in burn patients have been depression and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), which are present in 13–23% and 13–45% of cases, respectively. (10).

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted over six months in government “Tertiary Care Hospital” Burns and Plastic Surgery Centre Hayatabad Peshawar Pakistan. The duration of research was 6 months after approval of Institutional Review Board. Following the acceptance of the study synopsis. The sample size, calculated using the Rao Soft sample size calculator ensuring 9% Anticipated frequency; by keeping the CI 95% with 5% margin of error, the sample size was 282 participants which is taken on basis of previous record of six months OPD record. Participants were recruited using convenient sampling technique. The inclusion criteria encompassed participant’s age between 15 to 50 years. Total body surface area (TBSA) burn ≥ 10 . Burn due to any cause (flame, electrical, scald, chemical etc.) and thickness (superficial, mixed, deep). Known case of patients with 2nd, 3rd, and 4th degree burns. Exclusion criteria included Patient presented with recent (acute <1 months) burn. Patient have, mental disorder, drug addiction, chronic debilitating sickness. Patients having neurological condition like stroke, Parkinson and Alzheimer diseases and patient with first degree burn were excluded from study. When the ethical clearance was taken from Ethical Review Committee of City University, Peshawar. After that concerned hospital/department was approached for data collection approval. **Ethical approval number 006-009/REB/BPSC/24.** Data collection involved participants were selected from the outpatient department. The participants were interviewed in waiting room of OPD. Participants were screened keeping the selection criterion in mind. The questionnaire was administered by face-to-face interview individually. Participants were assessed and Data was collected through English version of European quality of life questionnaire (EQ-5D-3L) and patient health questionnaire (PHQ-9) for depression. Before data collection, verbal and written consent was taken from participants. All the data was confidential. Statistical analyses were done using software IBM SPSS version 23. The qualitative data were expressed in frequency and percentages and the quantitative data expressed as mean and standard deviations. The relationship between two or more categorical variables was analyzed by Chi-square Test. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$ for all statistical tests, indicating a statistically significant association between variables if the p-value was less than 0.05

Result

During the six-month data collection period, the study included a sample of 282 patients who had experienced post-burn injuries and sought treatment at the outpatient department of the burn care center. The participants had an average age of 33.71 years, ranging from 18 to 50 years, with a standard deviation of ± 10.358 . The majority of the participants i.e. 117 individuals (41.5%) fall within the range of 31 to 45 years. Male were the predominant gender making up to 168 individuals (59.6%) of the sample. The study included 282 participants, out of which 168 were males (59.6%) and 114 were females (40.4%). descriptive statistic of causes of burn in which Flame burns accounted for most common cause of burn injuries, comprising 161 individuals (57.1%), electrical burn 43 (15.2%), Scald burn 34 cases (12.1%), chemical burn 28 (9.9%) and Thermal burn 16 (5.7%). The descriptive statistic of degree of burn in which 199 participants had second degree burn, 70 participants with third degree burn and 13 participants had 4th degree burn.

Table 1: Causes of burn in relation with gender

Gender		Flame	Electrical	Chemical	Thermal	Scald	Total
Male	Count	87	27	26	9	19	168
	% Percent	51.8%	16.1%	15.5%	5.4%	11.3%	100.0%
Female	Count	74	16	2	7	15	114
	% Percent	64.9%	14.0%	1.8%	6.1%	13.2%	100.0%
Total	Count	161	43	28	16	34	282
	% Percent	57.1%	15.2%	9.9%	5.7%	12.1%	100.0%

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Table 2: Parameters of Burn Injury

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Mode Of Incident		
Accidental	251	89.0
Suicidal	14	5.0
Homicidal	17	6.0
Total	282	100.0
Categories Of TBSA		
10-20	54	19.1
21-30	87	30.9
31-40	70	24.8
41-60	56	19.9
61-80	12	4.3
81-100	3	1.1
Total	282	100.0
Degree Of Burn		
2nd Degree	199	70.6
3rd Degree	70	24.8
4th Degree	13	4.6
Total	282	100.0
Duration Of Hospital Stay		
Less Than 15 Days	176	62.4
Less Than 30	80	28.4
More Than One Month	26	9.2
Total	282	100.0

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Health-Related Quality of Life in Post-Burn Patients

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Mobility		
no problem	85	30.1
moderate problem	96	34.0
severe problem	101	35.8
Total	282	100.0
Self-care		
no problem	61	21.6
moderate problem	134	47.5
severe problem	87	30.9
Total	282	100.0
Usual activity		
no problem	24	8.5
moderate problem	116	41.1
severe problem	142	50.4
Total	282	100.0
Pain/discomfort		
no problem	61	21.6
moderate problem	134	47.5
severe problem	87	30.9
Total	282	100.0
Anxiety and depression		

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no problem	96	34.0
moderate problem	106	37.6
severe problem	78	27.7
Total	282	100.0
vertical visual analoge scale		
0-25	40	14.2
26-50	113	40.1
51-75	99	35.1
76-100	30	10.6
Total	282	100.0

The relation of QOL with gender which is the result of chi square test. The association of mobility with gender the p-value is higher than 0.5 at 0.849. Hence there is no significant association of mobility with gender. Association of self-care with gender the p-value is 0.4 which shows strong association between two variables. Association between anxiety and depression with gender is strong because p-value is 0.00 which is smaller than 0.5. The P-value among two variables i.e. pain/discomfort and gender is 0.00 which is less than 0.5 so it shows strong association between these two variables. Association between usual activity and gender is strong because p-value is 0.02 which is smaller than 0.5 so there is strong relation among these two variables. The association of VAS with gender is strong because the p-value is 0.37 which is less than 0.5.

Table 4: Descriptive analysis of depression in post burn patients

PHQ-9 score		Frequency	Percent
Depression	minimal (1-4)	48	17.0
	mild (5-9)	53	18.8
	moderate (10-14)	57	20.2
	moderate severe (15-19)	44	15.6
	severe (20-27)	80	28.4
	Total	282	100.0

Table 5: Depression relation with gender

Gender	PHQ-9 score for depression					Total	p-value
	minimal (1-4)	mild (5-9)	moderate (10-14)	moderate severe (15-19)	severe (20-27)		
Male	34	28	33	21	52	168	0.12
Female	14	25	24	23	28	114	
Total	48	53	57	44	80	282	

Discussion

The study consists of 282 participants among these 168 were male and 114 were female. The participants had mean age of 33.71 years, ranging from 18 to 50 years, with a standard deviation of ± 10.358 . The majority of the participants i.e. 117 individuals (41.5%) fall within the range of 31 to 45 years. Male were the predominant gender making up to 168 individuals (59.6%) of the sample. Our current study finding show that Burn injuries are more common in men participants as compared to female. This might be the men engaging in more outside activities. Moreover, alcoholism and/or drug addiction are more common in men and can result in unintentional injury, assault, vehicle explosions, suicide attempts, and accidental injuries our finding is supported by a study (24.)

According to the findings of current study, the majority of participants had moderate-to-severe problems with their regular activities (50.4.1%), self-care limitations (46.8%), mobility issues (35.8%), depression/anxiety (67.1%), and difficulty carrying out their regular activities (59.2%). This finding is supported by a study of (4) (25). In our current study depression had high prevalence in male participant, this

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finding is supported by a study (22). Regarding gender and age, there were no discernible changes in the study population's EQ-5D and VAS ratings. This is in opposition to certain earlier research. Although the current study showed that women's quality of life was not appreciably lower than men. This result runs counter to other studies that claim women who suffer burn injuries frequently have a lower quality of life. This makes sense that women have fewer rights to social assistance and have emotional and avoidant coping mechanisms, all of which have a detrimental impact on how well they adjust to life following burn injuries (24), (43). In our current study depression was high in male. However, this result is not supported by a previous study (24)

The mean age of the burn patients in current study was 33.71 ± 10.358 years, which is similar with the finding of other previous study (24). Our study finding shows that Flame burn were the most prevalent type of burn these finding is supported by a study (24), Regarding age groups, findings of the current study align with some other research (43), (39), (27), In the current study depression had high prevalence in male patients, which is consistent with many other studies (24, 42). However, it contradicts two studies which showed a higher prevalence of depression (almost the reverse) in females (41) (45).

According to our current study the relationship between QOL and the total body surface area concerned was inverse. The likelihood of having a low quality of life increased with the amount of the body surface area involved. A comparable association was shown in a study (24). Our current study observed that total body surface area (%TBSA), duration of when burn injury occurred, and degree of burn had significant influence on both psychological and physical outcomes measured by EQ-5D. Patients with significant burns, regarding the degree of burns and %TBSA, reported impaired quality of life, these finding are aligning with findings from other studies. (39), (27).

Conclusion

It is concluded from this study that there is significant association among burns, Quality of life and depression. Certain dimensions of quality of life such as mobility, self-care, usual activity anxiety and pain and discomfort was significantly affected in post burns patients with p-value of 0.03 for mobility and less than 0.001 for all other dimensions respectively. Similarly, significant association is observed in post burn patients and depression i.e., P-value = 0.005. Moreover, depression was found most prevalent in males than females i.e., p-valve = 0.12 and male 30% and female 24% respectively.

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